

PROJECT DELIVERABLE

Project acronym: **TRUSTyFOOD**

Project title: **Stakeholders-driven pathways for blockchain implementation in the agri-food sector**

Grant Agreement number: 101060534

<i>WP No</i>	<i>Deliverable related No</i>	<i>Deliverable No</i>	<i>Deliverable name</i>	<i>Lead beneficiary</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Dissemination level</i>	<i>Due date</i>
3	D3.1	D8	Stakeholder engagement plan	6. STICHTING VU	R	PU	30/06/2023 – M12

Actual submission date: 30/06/2023 – M12

Funded by
the European Union

Document information

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Project funding

Grant Agreement n.: 101060534 — TRUSTyFOOD — HORIZON-CL6-2021-FARM2FORK-01-07

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Executive summary

This document outlines the Stakeholder Engagement Plan that will be undertaken as part of the TRUSTyFOOD project. Prior to the stakeholder engagement activities, a survey was conducted targeting both players who already experienced blockchain technology (BCT) and actors within the agrifood sector to understand perspectives on and experiences with digital technology, and to understand how innovative technologies can fit into the agrifood system. Insights were generated which guided the subsequent stakeholder engagement activities.

To be inclusive, there are four avenues through which stakeholders will be engaged throughout the course of this process: sectoral Working Groups (WGs), local Focus Groups (FGs), Clustering Group (CG), and inter-sectoral Task Forces (TFs).

Sectoral Working Groups will involve a wide range of stakeholders operating within the broader agrifood sector. These working groups will cover the most substantive part of the overall stakeholder engagement process and will be focused on developing content and input for the “R&I Roadmap for blockchain technology’s implementation in the agri-food sector” (the expected main output of the project), as a portfolio of R&I priorities and activities for the decade to come.

The local Focus Groups will refine and build on the insights of the WGs in light of local contextual factors, to ensure the roadmap will take these contextual factors into account.

The inter-sectoral task forces represent a group of BCT experts that are not limited to the agrifood sector. The TFs will be primarily concerned with the development of three white/position papers on specific high-level discussions, as stipulated in the project Document of Action.

Finally, the Clustering Group will represent, at a high level, the target audience for dissemination and communication of project results. Such a group will not contribute directly to content development, but – as a sort of Advisory Board – will provide updates on policies and regulations, advice, and recommendations to be taken into consideration in the drafting of the final documents.

This plan outlines the implementation and monitoring activities as well as measures to manage data for the integrity of the project.

Glossary:

“Stakeholder Board”: a group or committee composed of stakeholders

“Stakeholder”: an individual or group who is responsible for, or affected by BCT and BCT-related decisions.

“Engagement”: taking part and/or sharing in the activities of a group. It also implies a moral commitment or binding promise. In a partnership context, engagement may best be understood by identifying in what ways different stakeholders might most appropriately take part in its work (L. Scott, 2009).

Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
BCT	Blockchain technology
CG	Clustering group
FG	Focus Group
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IT	Information Technology
IoT	Internet of Things
R&I	Research & Innovation
SEP	Stakeholder Engagement Plan
SH	Stakeholder
TF	Task Force
WG	Working Group

1. Introduction

1.1 TRUSTyFOOD project in brief

Blockchain (BCT) is an emerging technology, which has received much attention in recent years, with also very conflicting opinions. On the one hand, some public debates argue that blockchain is all hype and still hasn't proven its reliability across most industries and that the buzz around this technology has simply been generated to attract investments; on the other hand, experts in the field declare that BCT is a technology that is almost certain to have profound societal and economic impact in the next years and that it can offer opportunities to different sectors, agri-food included. Such uncertainty on one side and the rapid and unpredictable direction of blockchain innovation makes it particularly hard to make strategic decisions on this topic.

The TRUSTyFOOD project intends to shed light on the current partial and fragmented picture of BCT applications in the agri-food domain, by clarifying the benefits and opportunities which BCT can concretely afford to stakeholders throughout the food chain, and by providing the most suitable tool to each targeted stakeholder for prompt, easy, and effective implementation in their own context. It intends to draw up an R&I Roadmap for BCT's application in the agri-food sector to prepare the way for R&I activities for the decade to come. Within the Roadmap, R&I priorities will be identified and organized in research areas and functionalities. Each research area will help facilitating collaboration between European Institutions, industry, and research institutes while collectively developing a shared repository of ideas. The R&I roadmap will indicate intervention actions and investments necessary to close the gaps between BCT's capabilities and user requirements. Its purpose is to ensure that future blockchain-based services and decisions comply with user expectations, taking in great consideration the peculiarities of the agri-food sector.

The main phases are as follows:

- **Mapping, collecting and assessing**

Due to the novelty and elusiveness of BCT, there is no ready-to-use analytical framework yet for assessing its applicability. The project intends to provide an analytical framework for understanding and comparing different blockchain applications, collecting information, experiences and best practices, including those coming from other sectors, which can become effective in the food domain. The project will carry out an in-depth contextual analysis, through desk research. Starting from a wide number of real-world case studies, the consortium will identify working practices, implementation techniques, and remaining gaps. Results will be summarized in Deliverable 2.1, public.

- **Discussion with supply chain players and experts in BCTs**

The desk research cannot be exhaustive and some discussions and working groups need to be activated along the project lifespan to fill in the missing information, confirm or revise preliminary findings emerging from secondary research and define recommendations for the future. The best way to understand is directly from people who are working on BCT's application, who have experienced challenges, failures, successes and can provide interesting insights. To ensure the project reaches its goal it requires advice, assistance, participation and knowledge from a wide range of stakeholders.

The Consortium intends to apply **innovative participatory method** for co-creating throughout the project and for this purpose to set up a stable and active **Stakeholder Board**.

1.2 Conceptualising ‘Stakeholder Engagement’

Deverka et al. (2012) define stakeholder engagement as “an iterative process of actively soliciting the knowledge, experience, judgment and values of individuals selected to represent a broad range of direct interest in a particular issue, for the dual purposes of: creating a shared understanding; making relevant, transparent and effective decisions”.

Stakeholder engagement in TRUSTyFOOD is vital to ensure research is relevant, accessible and useful to end-users. A Stakeholder Board acts as a platform for communication, collaboration, and consultation. By involving stakeholders throughout the project, transparency, inclusivity, and accountability in the decision-making processes in the project will be fostered. This approach recognizes that the interests of various stakeholders are interconnected and that their involvement can contribute to more informed, balanced, and sustainable outcomes.

Stakeholders will not be represented only by farmers or food producers (intended them as the final ‘end-users’ of the technology), but to all the indirect players involved in BCT application, that is: IT solution providers (including providers and developers of IT infrastructure, software platforms and APPs), investors, devices developers (e.g., IoT, AI), etc. The project will investigate and discuss both technical aspects through the involvement of experts as well as non-technical barriers to BCTs deployment, the main points of focus being its potential benefits and drawbacks from the perspective of farmers and other supply chain players, mitigation of negative environmental impacts and ensuring finance for adoption.

1.3 Stakeholder Engagement Plan: what is it?

A stakeholder engagement plan (SEP) is a written document that is formulated before activity with stakeholders begins, and which is kept on file and updated over the course of the project as necessary. Its purpose is to identify the project’s key stakeholders, and to outline a methodology and approach for how the project team will interact and communicate with those stakeholders.

1.4 Importance of the Stakeholder Engagement Plan

TRUSTyFOOD project not only includes stakeholders; they also play a fundamental role in the achievement of its final goals. Stakeholders can include individuals, groups, or organizations who have an interest in the success of the project for personal and professional reasons.

Stakeholders can hold tremendous sway over how a project progresses. They authorize and allocate resources to the project, and may also decide to pause or stop their collaboration completely if they feel that it is not delivering the expected or desired outcome. It is crucial that the project team outline a way of managing these expectations because all stakeholders will be engaged to a different degree, and may have their own motivations or expectations for the project.

1.5 Validity of the Stakeholder Engagement Plan

The Plan will be in force until the end of the project (expected on 30 June 2025).

Even if it has been drafted with a reasonable level of accuracy, since the project is still at an early stage and some external factors can change the perspectives (e.g. reflect on emerging consultation dynamics, new methods, regulations, market, etc), the document will be revised along the project lifespan to confirm or eventually re-align contents.

1.6 Stakeholder Engagement Plan: the structure of the document

The SEP will include the following parts:

i) Clarification of Stakeholder Board's Role

This section will clearly define the scope and objectives of the Stakeholder Board inside the project.

ii) Stakeholder Engagement Strategy

This section will present the approach used along the Stakeholders' engagement phase.

iii) Identification of Stakeholders

This section is used to identify all of the project's stakeholders to be involved. At a minimum, the section also defines their roles and responsibilities as they relate to the project.

iv) Planning to Interact with the Stakeholders

This section will determine how the project team will interact and engage with the stakeholders identified in the first portion of the plan.

v) Stakeholder Engagement Activities

The final portion of the plan is essentially an outline of the various activities the project team will undertake to collaborate with stakeholders, manage their expectations, and keep them engaged with the project. This includes a consultation plan (outlining the types of groups that will be set up throughout the project and what is best suited for), but also activities such as pre-planned meetings with stakeholders or key reports.

vi) Monitoring and evaluation

The project team will use feedback to revise plan as needed.

1.7 Stakeholder Board role into the project

The Stakeholder Board will consist of a diverse representation of stakeholders to ensure inclusion of a comprehensive range of perspectives and to avoid biases.

Its role is to provide strategic guidance, review project plans, and ensure that blockchain applications align with the interests and requirements of stakeholders involved in the agri-food supply chain.

The Stakeholder Board serves to enhance the project in many ways:

- by bringing practitioners' knowledge into the project. Such knowledge can help to value the possible economic, social, and environmental costs and benefits of blockchain applications in different cases, and prompt the right questions;
- by bringing in views from outside of its partners' circle – for example, suggesting unexplored pathways in the process development or application;
- by verifying activities as they mature and bringing a positive critique to enable improvement of the project as work progresses;
- by linking with ongoing or completed projects and research which may help influence the project, and in turn, may give those other projects useful new knowledge and relationships;
- by acting as a sounding board and discussion platform to talk through specific elements of the project and to help find solutions to specific barriers;

- by linking the project to a wider industrial, research, and policy landscape;
- by putting into practice research results, exposing to proposed actions real end-users who are able to provide some level of buy-in or consensus.

Stakeholder Board Objectives

Through sharing knowledge generated during the project and expertise among stakeholders, this Board aims to:

- a. Help define stakeholders' needs and expectations from end user sector to market exploitation.
- b. Gather information for helping identify technical, environmental, regulatory, economic, and social barriers and constraints along the whole supply chain to BCT's application.
- c. Give recommendations and suggestions about the feasibility of blockchain along scenarios that will be investigated and found during the project.
- d. Giving support to elaborate well-targeted dissemination material and spread it around through the communication networks of stakeholders themselves.

2. Stakeholder engagement strategy

2.1 Transdisciplinary approach

For the stakeholder engagement we make use of a transdisciplinary approach. A transdisciplinary approach is important in stakeholder engagement because it recognizes the complexity and interconnectedness in the application of BCT in the agri-food supply chain. By bringing together individuals or groups with diverse perspectives, interests, and expertise to participate in decision-making processes, the approach contributes towards:

- 1. Comprehensive understanding:** Stakeholder engagement on the application of BCT in the agri-food sector involves addressing multifaceted problems that require input from various disciplines and perspectives. By adopting a transdisciplinary approach, stakeholders ranging from farmers to consumer organizations can collectively explore different dimensions and gain a more comprehensive understanding of the complexities. This approach allows for the integration of diverse knowledge, theories, methods, and perspectives, leading to more informed decision-making.
- 2. Collaborative problem-solving:** The transdisciplinary approach promotes collaboration and cooperation among stakeholders who under normal conditions would not interact directly with each other. It encourages the exchange of knowledge, expertise, and ideas across disciplines, fostering a shared understanding and a sense of collective ownership over the decision-making process.
- 3. Holistic perspective:** Many challenges faced by stakeholders in the application of blockchain in the agri-food supply chain span multiple sectors, disciplines, and scales. By adopting a transdisciplinary approach, stakeholders can examine issues from a holistic perspective, considering social, economic, environmental, and cultural factors. This broader view allows for a more balanced and inclusive decision-making process, where the potential impacts and trade-offs of different actions are thoroughly evaluated.
- 4. Enhanced legitimacy and credibility:** Stakeholder engagement processes are often designed to ensure that decisions are fair, transparent, and credible. This is particularly important for emerging technologies such as blockchain which promise potential benefits on one hand while bringing risks and uncertainties on the other hand. A transdisciplinary approach strengthens the legitimacy of the decision-making process by involving a diverse range of stakeholders and considering multiple perspectives. This inclusivity and openness contribute to increased trust, acceptance, and buy-in from stakeholders, making the decisions more robust and effective for road mapping.
- 5. Innovation and creativity:** The transdisciplinary approach encourages thinking beyond disciplinary boundaries and promotes innovation and creativity. By bringing together individuals with different backgrounds, expertise, and ways of thinking, stakeholders can challenge established assumptions, explore new approaches, and generate novel ideas. This interdisciplinary collaboration can lead to innovative solutions and more effective strategies for addressing complex problems faced by the stakeholders across the agri-food supply chain.
- 6. Long-term sustainability:** Many stakeholder engagement processes involve issues related to sustainability and long-term planning. The transdisciplinary approach is well-suited for addressing sustainability challenges as it allows for the integration of diverse perspectives, including environmental, social, and economic dimensions. By considering the interdependencies and interactions between these aspects, stakeholders can

develop more robust and resilient strategies that promote sustainable development and long-term well-being. This is important in the TRUSTyFOOD project in which environmental sustainability is emphasized as a cross-cutting theme.

2.2 Identification of Stakeholders

When engaging stakeholders, it is important to first outline a systematic process as to how relevant stakeholders will be identified. The following steps will be taken:

- 1. Identify stakeholder categories:** Start by identifying broad categories of stakeholders that are likely to be impacted by or have an influence on the blockchain application. These categories may include farmers, producers, distributors, retailers, consumer organisations, government agencies, industry associations, technology providers, financial institutions, and regulatory bodies.
- 2. Conduct stakeholder mapping:** Create a stakeholder map or matrix to visually represent the identified stakeholder categories. Map stakeholders based on their level of influence, interest, or potential impact on the blockchain application. Consider both direct stakeholders who are directly involved in the agri-food supply chain and indirect stakeholders who may have an indirect influence or interest. *Note:* this step was conducted with all consortium partners during the second consortium meeting in February 2023.
- 3. Exploratory research and analysis:** Conduct exploratory research to gather information on each stakeholder category. Understand their roles, responsibilities, concerns, interests, and potential benefits or challenges related to the implementation of blockchain in the agri-food supply chain. Consult existing literature, industry reports, government documents, and engage with experts to gather insights.
- 4. Identify specific stakeholders:** Within each stakeholder category, identify specific stakeholders who fall within the defined scope and have a significant impact or interest. Although committees/boards are composed of organisational and institutional members from different sectors, they are initiated and driven by individuals acting on their behalf. Consider key decision-makers, influencers, subject matter experts, community leaders, and organizations that represent the interests of certain stakeholder groups.
- 5. Prioritise stakeholders:** Prioritize stakeholders based on their level of influence, their potential impact on the success of the blockchain application, and the extent to which they are affected by it. This prioritization will help allocate resources and determine the level of engagement required for each stakeholder.

The stakeholder identification process is an iterative process, and stakeholders may evolve or change throughout the project lifecycle. It is therefore important to regularly review and update the stakeholder mapping as new stakeholders emerge or existing stakeholders' interests and influence shift.

2.3 List of the categories

When considering the application of blockchain in the agri-food supply chain, many stakeholders may be involved. The added value each category can bring into the project is clarified below; in any case, the consortium considers that all of them have the same importance into the project, without levels of influence, confirming in this way that the approach is oriented to inclusiveness.

SH1: Farmers/producers: Representatives from agricultural and farming communities who can provide insights into the specific needs, challenges, and requirements of primary producers in the supply chain. Farmers employing organic and other alternative production systems may be specifically included as relevant.

SH2: Agri-food supply chain players: Representatives from agri-food supply chain actors, exclusive of farmers and consumers. Therefore, this category includes food processing, manufacturing companies, wholesalers, etc. who can provide insights into the various stages of the agri-food supply chain in between farm and fork. Actors involved in organic, green, bio-based, or other alternative supply chains may be specifically included as relevant.

SH3: Consumers: Representatives from consumer advocacy groups or organizations who can represent the interests and concerns of consumers in terms of food safety, sustainability, and ethical considerations.

SH4: Technology providers: Representatives from blockchain technology companies or solution providers with expertise in developing and implementing blockchain applications in the agri-food sector.

SH5: Investors and BCT associations: The investors and blockchain technology associations play a significant role in supporting and funding blockchain projects in the agri-food supply chain. They provide financial resources to start-ups, companies, or initiatives that are developing and implementing blockchain solutions. They include venture capital firms, angel investors, impact investors, strategic partners, or other funding organizations.

SH6: Policy makers, auditors, and certifications bodies: Stakeholders from relevant government bodies responsible for agriculture, food safety, regulation, and policymaking. Their involvement is crucial for addressing regulatory compliance, legal considerations, and fostering collaboration between public and private sectors. Often, they are already involved in funded EC projects as partners.

SH7: Academia/research Institutions: Representatives from research institutions or academic experts specializing in agriculture, supply chain management, blockchain technology, or related fields who can contribute their research, knowledge, and insights.

SH8: Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs): Representatives from relevant NGOs or sustainability-focused organizations who can provide perspectives on social and environmental aspects, as well as advocate for responsible and ethical practices in the agri-food supply chain. The stakeholders are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Overview of broad categories of stakeholders.

Figure 1 represents the traditional Farm-to-Fork food supply chain (from farm to consumer). However, recently the concept of “food value chain” is expanding its boundaries. Therefore, as discussed above, attention will be paid to the inclusion of farmers and other food supply chain actors who are involved in organic, green, bio-based, and other alternative supply chains.

2.4 Mapping stakeholders

Once the project team identified the stakeholder types to involve, the following step consists in working on finding them. It may be useful to create a map or list of specific stakeholders to connect with into a table or spreadsheet (Table 1).

Table 1. Spreadsheet for mapping stakeholders

Partner in charge	Stakeholders' details						What kind of expertise will the stakeholder bring to TRUSTyFOOD?	Category/Target group	Criteria for selection	NOTES
	Name, Surname	Gender	Country	Name of organisation	Sector	Email address				

Once stakeholder maps are created, it is important to keep them up to date if they are to be used again, as stakeholder information and relevance of stakeholders is likely to change over time.

2.5 Recruitment strategies

Recruitment started along the first year of the project through the Surveys. Indeed, the last point of the questionnaire asked people to express interest in joining the Stakeholder Board. This mechanism allowed to the project to have a preliminary list of stakeholders ready at M12.

In addition, the following strategies will be activated along the project lifespan:

1) Search for stakeholders

- **Leveraging existing relationships:** The possibility to involve experts from existing relationships is the best and winning strategy; this includes determining if colleagues have existing relationships with relevant stakeholders. It may be appropriate to ask colleagues for contact details or an introduction to personalise contacts and give a direct route into an organisation.
- **Existing projects on the topic:** European Commission funded projects have large visibility through the web (e.g. CORDIS). From there it is possible to analyse partners and roles, reach publications, speeches in public conferences, public interviews which show the expertise of specific people to be involved into the stakeholder board.
- **Social media:** Social media has made it easier to reach people. (Appel et al., 2020). LinkedIn, for example, provides a unique opportunity and resource for stakeholder engagement. Twitter, also, is an important mean for sharing messages.
- **Peer reviewed publications:** Experts are often authors/co-authors of documents on the topic. From there it is possible to identify candidates to be involved, searching then for their affiliation and related public references.
- **Events:** Network at events (even online events) to connect with stakeholders. If you are trying to link in with an organisation, talk to people at events to find connections. They may not be the right people, but it is likely that they will know of the right people to contact.
- **Snowballing:** Stakeholders are asked to suggest further stakeholders who continue to suggest further stakeholders

2) Let stakeholders come to us

It is planned to activate by July 2023 **a specific area on the project website which will promote the Stakeholder Board**. Interested parties who consult the website have access to a template for profiling themselves and joining the list of stakeholders. Additionally, the website will be advertised through relevant channels (e.g., LinkedIn).

2.6. Identification of benefits and incentives

A Stakeholder is affected by or has an impact on the activities, decisions, and outcomes coming from the project. Long discussions have been carried out inside the consortium to identify levers of interest (benefits).

In general terms the following two points are considered valid for all the categories:

- The project may provide insights and findings that would otherwise not have heard of (first-hand results). Results can be useful to them to take internal decisions, manage internal processes, procedures, and manage in a trustworthy and transparent way relationships along their supply chains.
- Networking and cultivation of social relationships: the Stakeholder Board offers networking opportunities for stakeholders to meet with other stakeholders and establish collaborations with them.

Then, there are benefits specific for each category (Table 2):

Table 2. Potential benefits for category

Stakeholder	Potential benefits of increased engagement
Farmers and other food supply chain players	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Results in evidence that is relevant to food supply chain players. • Food system is influenced by the best available evidence. • Food supply chain players are better able to understand blockchain and take related decisions. • Improved awareness on BCT among food supply chain players
Policy-makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improves the translation of research into policy and practice, • Improved contextualization of BCT evidence so that it can be used in guidelines and policy. • Improved awareness of BCT among policy makers and agriculture officers.
Technology providers and investors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking with potential future clients • Technology scouting and benchmarking • Improved awareness on food system and its real needs and opportunities
Researchers and BCT Associations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Results in evidence that is relevant to researchers and their job • Primary research that is better designed to fit knowledge gap and research needs. • Opportunities for future investments or projects. • Improved awareness on BCT in the scientific community
Consumer organizations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotes transparency, accountability, and trust in the way that research is produced • Results in evidence that addresses consumers' needs • Improved awareness about blockchain technology among consumers and the public.

3. Stakeholder engagement methods

3.1 The consultation process

There are various methods and approaches that will be used along the stakeholders' consultation process, depending on the context and expected goals. The methods that we consider applicable for the stakeholder engagement activities in TRUSTyFOOD are:

- 1. Surveys and questionnaires¹:** Surveys and questionnaires are effective tools for gathering structured feedback from stakeholders. Since blockchain technology is an emerging technology, surveys are useful in providing an overview of the current state of the technology. They can be administered online, via email, or through paper-based formats. Surveys allow for quantitative analysis and can reach a large number of stakeholders, providing insights on their opinions, preferences, and needs.
- 2. Interviews²:** Interviews provide an opportunity for in-depth exploration of stakeholders' perspectives, experiences, and insights regarding blockchain in the agri-food supply chain. Through one-on-one conversations, interviewees can express their opinions, concerns, and suggestions in a more detailed and personalized manner. This allows for a deeper understanding of their unique perspectives and helps identify specific challenges and opportunities. They can be conducted in person, over the phone, or via video calls. They are particularly useful when engaging with key individuals or representatives of stakeholder groups
- 3. Focus groups:** Focus groups involve bringing together a small group of stakeholders to facilitate discussion and gather qualitative insights. They allow for a deeper exploration of stakeholders' perspectives, experiences, and concerns related to the implementation of blockchain technology in the agri-food supply chain. The interactive nature of focus group discussions promotes a rich exchange of ideas, enabling stakeholders to share their insights and provide detailed feedback on the potential benefits, challenges, and implications of using blockchain. Skilled facilitators will guide the conversation on specific topics, allowing participants to share their perspectives, experiences, and suggestions.
- 4. Workshops and co-creation sessions:** Workshops and co-creation sessions bring together stakeholders from diverse backgrounds, including farmers, producers, distributors, retailers, consumer advocacy groups, technology experts, and policymakers. By facilitating collaborative discussions, these sessions leverage the collective intelligence of participants. The diverse perspectives and expertise contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities of implementing blockchain in the agri-food supply chain. Workshops and co-creation sessions offer a platform for stakeholders to work together in solving practical challenges related to blockchain implementation. Participants can share their first-hand experiences and insights, identify specific pain points, and collectively develop strategies to overcome barriers. The interactive nature of these sessions facilitates a deeper understanding of the complexities involved and encourages the development

¹ The survey and questionnaires were implemented from April to June 2023.

² Some interviews were carried out from April to June 2023 from most of the beneficiaries (TCA, AFC, NSCE, FHG, CERTH, COMP, INOV)

of actionable and implementable solutions. They can involve activities such as brainstorming, group discussions, role-playing, or design thinking exercises.

- 5. Advisory committees and panels:** Advisory committees and panels bring together a diverse group of experts with specialised knowledge and experience in relevant fields. These experts may include representatives from academia, industry, technology, supply chain management, agriculture, and regulatory bodies. Their expertise and insights contribute to a deeper understanding of the potential applications, challenges, and opportunities of blockchain in the agri-food supply chain. They provide strategic guidance and recommendations based on their collective expertise. They can analyse the potential impact of blockchain technology on the agri-food supply chain, identify relevant use cases, and evaluate the feasibility of implementation. This guidance helps in making informed decisions, prioritising initiatives, and allocating resources effectively.

The next section focuses on the method 1 and 2 which consist of surveys/questionnaires and interviews which were implemented as preliminary actions related to the Stakeholder Engagement Plan.

3.2 Surveys and Interviews

Two surveys were created along the first year of the project: one addressed to stakeholders already experienced in BCT and another one addressed to food supply chain players only.

The first type of survey involved the whole consortium in the definition of its purpose, the target group, the geographical area covered, the specific questions and the communication channels for making it reachable. Dedicated meetings were organised at the scope. The questionnaire was created for multiple internal purposes, dividing the document into two main parts: i) technical questions, ii) more generic questions. It is intended to investigate the role that BCT can play in changing the agriculture and food system and understand the complex and rapidly changing landscape of blockchain solutions applied to food system challenges. An analysis of the use case surveys revealed that while BCT holds promise for the agri-food supply chain, there are several challenges that need to be addressed for its successful implementation. The challenges are multi-faceted, for example integrating blockchain technology into existing agri-food supply chain systems can be complex. This emanates from the fact that many organisations already have established databases, legacy systems, and IT infrastructure. Ensuring seamless integration between blockchain and these systems requires careful planning and coordination. In addition, the process of implementing BCT requires investment in infrastructure, including hardware, software, and network resources. These costs may pose a challenge for smaller farmers or organisations with limited resources. As BCT in the agri-food supply chain involves multiple stakeholders, including farmers, producers, processors, distributors, regulators, and consumers, it is difficult to develop governance models, define roles and responsibilities, and foster collaboration among the diverse entities.

Another survey was created expressly for food players and involved key partners in this endeavour, i.e. Agrifood Croatia, Confagricoltura, Tecnoalimenti, and NSCE. The purpose of this survey was to assess digital maturity of the agri-food sector by targeting agriculture, aquaculture, and food industries in order to gain insights into the adoption and potential of digital technologies within the agri-food system.

In particular, the survey aimed to depict the status-quo and achieve the following objectives:

- 1. Understanding stakeholder perspectives:** The survey helped to understand stakeholders' current knowledge, experiences, and understanding of digital technology. It provided insights into the level of digital maturity in the agri-food supply chain.
- 2. Identifying perceived benefits:** The survey sought to identify stakeholders' perceived benefits of digital technologies in the agri-food supply chain. It helped to capture their views on how the existing skills in digital technologies can be deployed to modern technologies such as blockchain.
- 3. Assessing perceived challenges:** By asking stakeholders about the challenges or obstacles they see in implementing digital technologies, the survey aimed to gather valuable input on potential barriers to adoption. It helped to identify concerns related to implementation costs, technical expertise, data privacy, security, and resistance to change.

Overall, the survey aimed to gather comprehensive information and insights from stakeholders to inform decision-making, strategic planning, and implementation of digital technologies in the agri-food supply chain. A total of 58% of the respondents expressed a specific interest in leveraging technological advancements that can render data immutable, ensuring authentication and combating counterfeiting. A significant 50% of the respondents revealed that they were unaware of blockchain technology and exhibited no interest in it. Among those who had acquired knowledge or direct experience with blockchain technology, 46% pointed out that they possessed only a rudimentary understanding obtained through independent research or limited exposure. Only a single company asserted having practical experience in applying blockchain technology. It emerged from the survey that the primary obstacles concerning investments in modern technologies are the associated costs, time requirements, internal skill gaps, and concerns over potential impacts on productivity.

Both surveys' results will represent the starting point for the identification of Topics to be brought under discussion in the following phase (Groups).

Following the analysis of the survey, more qualitative approaches to stakeholder engagement will be taken to get a more in-depth understanding of the different topics as outlined in section 4.

4. Groups for stakeholder engagement

Groups will be constituted both by project team researchers and non-partners (external stakeholders) selected from the Stakeholder Board.

Following the identification of stakeholders in section 2.2 and the elaboration of different potential methods in section 3, the approach for stakeholder engagement is outlined here. The stakeholder engagement activities are clustered into four specific types of groups: sectoral Working-Groups (WGs), sectoral local Focus Groups (FGs), Clustering Group, and inter-sectoral Task Forces (TFs). Engagement of these groups will take place in part consecutively, and in part in parallel, to allow an efficient process, while simultaneously allowing stakeholders in one group to follow up on findings of another group. The engagement of stakeholders will be done strategically in four different groups depending on the topic under discussion. A summary of the function of each group is given below (Table 3):

Table 3. Function of each group

What	Who	Level	Role/Output generated
Sectoral Working groups (WGs)	Actors from R&I projects/use cases (financed with public or private funds)	Act at EU level	Will contribute to draw up R&I Roadmap and Guidelines for users
Sectoral local Focus Groups	Local food supply chain players → restricted meetings	Act at local level	Will contribute to draw up R&I Roadmap and Guidelines for users
Clustering Group	BCTs experts, Policy makers and authorities, Representatives of the domain	It acts at EU level	Strategic role (will not generate documents, but will represent a Target audience for dissemination of project's results)
Inter-sectoral Task Forces	Experts in BCTs from other sectors (finance, healthcare, etc)	Act at EU level	Will contribute to draw up n.3 White Papers

The composition of each group will be different with some groups being homogenous, while others will be heterogenous depending on the goal of the stakeholder engagement activities. The order of the groups is explained in figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Overview of stakeholder engagement activities.

To thoroughly allow the project to build on these findings, all meetings with these groups will (i) follow a semi-structured protocol, allowing for exploration of defined topics, while going more in-depth whenever warranted and (ii) be audio-recorded, transcribed and - where needed - translated into English, to be able to follow up with thematic content analysis.

Each group is explained in detail in the following sections.

4.1 Sectoral Working Groups (WGs)

The sectoral working groups will represent the primary component of the stakeholder engagement process. It will cover three overarching thematic areas – transparent and traceable supply chains; climate change mitigation and agriculture; and healthy, inclusive, and sustainable food systems (figure 3) – and explore how BCT may be leveraged within each area. A wide range of relevant stakeholders will be involved, in both homogenous and heterogeneous groups, throughout this process; the broad groups of stakeholders are summarized in table 4.

Figure 3: Overarching themes guiding the stakeholder engagement process. Sectoral Working Groups

Table 4. Breakdown of broad categories of stakeholders Stakeholder Groups: Sectoral Working Groups

SH1	Farmers and their organizations
SH2	Agrifood players (processors, retailers)
SH3	Consumer organizations
SH4	Technology providers
SH5	Investors and BCT associations
SH6	Policymakers, auditors, and certification bodies
SH7	Academia/research Institutions
SH8	Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs)

The engagement of sectoral working groups will proceed in four phases, which will be elaborated in detail below. The process will begin with visioning sessions, the objective of which is to outline the promises that BCT can afford to different actors and issues within the agri-food system. Visioning sessions will be conducted with heterogeneous groups of the various stakeholders. Following the visioning sessions, the engagement process will then explore gaps and barriers that exist between the present situation and the realization of future visions articulated in phase one. A key objective in this phase is to understand and articulate in detail *stakeholder-specific* barriers and gaps. Once gaps and barriers have been identified, the stakeholder engagement process will return to heterogeneous groups for the final phases of strategy co-creation and consolidation and reflection. In these final two phases, the objective of the engagement process will shift to co-creating a range of actionable strategies that will contribute to realization of the visions articulated in phase one; these two phases will produce and refine content for the R&I roadmap.

The stakeholder engagement process is designed reflexively – meaning that we will take findings of earlier phases into account when designing in detail later phases. Consequently, phase 1: Visioning is elaborated extensively below, while the details for later phases will be informed by findings from the stakeholder engagement in Phase 1, as well as the surveys conducted early 2023. Updates, additions and refinements to the stakeholder engagement plan will thus be made throughout the course of the project.

4.1.1 Phase 1: Visioning

The first phase that will be undertaken by the sectoral working groups is focused on deepening our understanding of previous assumptions and findings, as well as developing future visions of BCT's use in food systems. One of the core outputs of the TRUSTyFOOD project is an R&I Roadmap, which *“will indicate intervention actions and investments necessary to close the gaps between BCTs capabilities and user requirements”* (TRUSTyFOOD Grant Agreement, Annex 1). Visioning will provide the foundation from which such interventions, investments, and other strategies will be developed. A total of six sessions will be conducted during this phase, with two sessions for each of the three overarching themes. The groups of participants will be made up of a selection of all stakeholder types (table 4), and the selection of specific stakeholders will be made with reference to the overarching theme under discussion and the orientation and experience of individual stakeholders.

Visioning and stakeholder engagement

Visioning, or the development of “normative” (Vergagt and Quist, 2011; Jiren et al, 2023) or “ideal-type” (Brown, Harris, and Russell, 2010) scenarios of the future, is often used in multi-stakeholder research and is considered vital to such processes that aim to promote transformational change (Ibid). Such process “can lead to recommendations and even transformations of for instance food system (R&I) policies, priorities, strategies, investments, socioeconomic research and innovation systems, behaviours and attitudes, education, products and services” (Athena Institute, 2018a, p. 2).

Visioning sessions are carefully designed, and the topics of discussion are preempted (Davies, 2014). The themes, specific content, and specific questions of the visioning exercises are prompted by the researchers. In this case, input will be derived from existing academic literature, non-academic reports and other secondary sources, as well as the preliminary data collection and analysis performed in the TRUSTyFOOD project (D2.1, D2.2). Each session and its

theme will be introduced by the researchers/facilitators, for example by presenting a narrative of how global agricultural systems are currently contributing to climate change rather than mitigating it (in the case of the theme “climate change mitigation in agriculture), or by discussing the issues related to opacity within food supply chains (in the case of the theme “transparent and traceable supply chains”). Beginning the sessions in this way, following Davies (2014), will help to guide discussions and creativity towards relevant topics.

Visioning can take many methodological forms, which allows for its flexible and context-specific use. For example, the Horizon Project Fit4Food2030 made use of visioning at multiple stages of their project, both within the research consortium and in various stages while engaging with different stakeholders (Svare et al, 2020). In this project, visioning was done in City Labs to help “engage and motivate stakeholders around a shared objective”; and in policy labs “in conjunction with the mapping and assessment of national research and innovation systems”, as well as coinciding with “systematic mapping and analyses of national food systems, and [...] their strengths, challenges, knowledge gaps, and opportunities” (ibid). Visioning was a valuable component of the Fit4Food2030 project with multiple functions. The Fit4Food2030 project also provides resources for the design of specific workshops (Athena Institute, 2018a, b).

Numerous other projects and researchers employ visioning as a key methodology. For example, the EU-funded FUSILLI project (grant agreement No. 101000717) also developed a “shared vision of the future situation” as the first step in a participatory process aimed at developing long-term urban food plans (Jorge and Jorde, 2022). Additionally, Mandujano et al provide a conceptual framework for the ‘gamification’ of visioning and other foresight methodologies (2021). The authors argue that these tools can promote deeper engagement with a creativity during participation in visioning sessions, and these tools therefore represent an additional resource the research team may draw on in the development of each workshop’s activities (ibid).

One type of visioning that will be drawn on in this stakeholder engagement plan (considering phase 1 in concert with phases 2 and 3) is *backcasting*. Backcasting can be distinguished from a straightforward visioning exercise because “backcasting is not only about developing a vision, but also about developing *strategies and pathways* [about] how to eventually achieve those visions” (Vergagt and Quist, 2011; emphasis added). Ultimately, the objective of this stakeholder engagement process is to develop content and input for the R&I Roadmap (D5.1); the proximal objective of phase 1 is therefore to provide a concrete, shared starting point from which to develop interventions and other strategies for inclusion within the roadmap.

Given the proximal and ultimate objectives of the stakeholder engagement plan, visioning provides a valuable starting point, as beginning multi-stakeholder research processes with visioning can help drive discussions towards devising policy and practical strategies to promote change (Sheppard et al, 2011). Gaziulusoy and Ryan extend this point:

“when participants are invited to elaborate on specific details of a general normative vision [...] the elaborations can make visible the specific infrastructures, support systems, technologies, and institutional and socio-cultural arrangements which such visions necessitate, thereby revealing concrete instruments and levers for change which actions in the present may aim towards” (2017).

With appropriate research design and framing, visioning activities can be utilized to guide stakeholder engagement processes towards development of a range of specific strategies that may help to bring about the vision. The alignment between this methodology and the objectives of TRUSTyFOOD's stakeholder engagement as stipulated in the DOA means that visioning (and in particular backcasting from those visions) has a valuable role to play in this overall stakeholder engagement process and will guide the process to contribute meaningfully to the project outputs.

It is therefore critical that researchers engage with the perspectives and visions of a range of actors within this space, including technology developers, policymakers, investors, agrifood supply-chain actors, and farmers. Further, identifying and analyzing points of contradiction or conflict between the visions of different stakeholder positions will be invaluable for the development of strategies to promote the beneficial use of blockchain in the context of food systems (phase 3 of WGs in this stakeholder engagement plan). This is one of the key advantages of visioning methodologies, as they can make it possible to “learn from competing images of the future” (Johansson, 2021) and therefore to disentangle them, highlight their points of contestation and potential opportunities for collaboration or synergy.

Finally, it is relevant to highlight that the objective of this phase is not to *extract or identify* existing visions from participants, but rather to *co-create* visions collectively. *Co-creating* visions and including a broader range of SHs, is a key part of the transdisciplinary approach which helps to address power imbalances (who is producing the visions?), and in the long run to ensure broader/more equitable distribution of benefits. As noted in section 5.2-5.3, a number of specific methodologies and tools may be used within vision co-creation sessions, such as design thinking or the use of virtual whiteboards (e.g., Google Jamboards) or other online collaboration tools.

The primary outputs of this phase are visions, hopes, and expectations about the role that BCT can play in facilitating transformations towards a food system characterized by each of the three overarching themes. These visions may be relatively coherent or fragmented. Following the sessions, the researchers will consolidate and analyze the findings to identify key points or aspects of the different visions. This analysis will proceed with a structured approach, making use of thematic analysis using the software Atlas.ti. Such a systematic analysis will ensure consistency in data analysis and that all key themes and patterns within the data are identified. These consolidated visions will provide the starting point for subsequent phases of the Sectoral Working Groups.

The visioning phase, consisting of a total of six sessions as described above, will take place over the course of approximately two months, in October and November 2023 (Figure 4). Thematic analysis of the data from this phase, concurrent with preparation for phase 2, will take place subsequently in December 2023.

4.1.2: Phase 2: Barriers and Drivers

In phase two, stakeholders will be divided into homogenous groups, with two sessions per stakeholder type. The purpose of this grouping is to allow each stakeholder group to deeply reflect on and discuss the challenges, barriers, and drivers that they experience and perceive while avoiding potential conflict or opposition from other stakeholder groups. This way, the perspectives and needs of all stakeholder groups will be taken into account in the overall analysis, and particularly in the strategy co-creation that will take place subsequently.

Each of these sessions will begin with a presentation of the consolidated vision(s) derived from phase 1. From this starting point, participants will then work to identify barriers or gaps between the present situation and the future vision. The objective in this stage is to avoid discussions of *how* to overcome these gaps (the “how” will be the objective of phases 3 and 4), but instead to focus in detail on the gaps/barriers themselves.

The sessions will be thoroughly prepared beforehand, by collecting known barriers and drivers from literature, which will allow for probing. Simultaneously, the purpose of these sessions is to *start* with the barriers and drivers that are salient among participants and correspond to their own experiences. Phase 2 will take place approximately from January to March of 2024 (Figure 4).

Following these sessions, the consortium will analyze and consolidate the results for input in the subsequent phases. This analysis, as with phase 1, will be based on a thematic analysis using Atlas.ti. Such analysis will take place during April 2024, in between phases 2 and 3.

4.1.3: Phase 3: Strategy Co-creation

Phase 2 will produce a detailed breakdown of the different barriers and drivers that each stakeholder perceives and experiences. The objective of phase 3 will be to co-create and co-design different strategies to overcome these barriers. These strategies could take many forms, including policy interventions, technological or social innovations, and investment mechanisms, among others.

In this phase, the stakeholders will again be gathered in heterogeneous groups. At this point, it is envisioned that the strategy co-creation sessions will be organized around four special topic areas, presented below on table 5. These topic areas were identified in the project proposal as “main drivers” for discussion and represent key areas in which technical issues may need to be overcome. It is anticipated that each of the special topic areas will be addressed throughout the course of discussions that take place in phases 1 and 2. The researchers will consolidate and analyze discussions and statements relevant to each topic area, again primarily making use of thematic analysis and Atlas.ti software. These results will then be presented to participants at the beginning of each of the strategy co-creation sessions.

For example, aspects of the visions articulated in phase 1 may refer to a particular imagined ‘state’ of future interoperability. Similarly, specific issues related to interoperability may be identified as major barriers or gaps within phase 2. The phase 3 session on interoperability would then begin with the researchers presenting results regarding how interoperability fit into the visions and into barriers and drivers, setting the objective of the session to co-create strategies to overcome these gaps and realize the vision with reference to the special topic of interoperability. As such, this phase will make significant use of the outputs of phases 1 and 2 in guiding the specific areas and questions discussed under the umbrellas of the broader special topics.

The design of workshops in this phase will incorporate a range of methodologies specifically used for co-creation and co-design, which serve to meaningfully include participants in creative processes, as indicated in section 3 above. In addition to drawing on the methodological corpus of the Athena Institute (e.g., Athena Institute, 2018a,b), the design of sessions within this phase will also draw from the participatory and gamified backcasting methods described, respectively, by Davies (2014) and Mandujano et al (2021).

Table 5. *Special topic areas for discussion in phase 3*

Interoperability, Standardization, Regulation
Trustworthiness, Cybersecurity, Identity Management
Distributed Consensus, Smart Contracts
Scalability, Connections with the Internet of Things

After this phase, results will again be consolidated and subject to thematic analysis by the researchers. This will produce relatively concrete strategies and innovations that will be reflected upon in the subsequent, final phase.

Phase 3, consisting of a total of eight sessions (two for each special topic area outlined in table 5), will take place from May to October of 2024 (Figure 4). This phase will have a relatively longer duration than the other phases of the WGs, due to the summer months. It is as yet unclear how many sessions, if any, it will be possible to conduct during the summer while many prospective participants may be on their yearly holidays. As such, the length of this phase has been extended in anticipation that sessions can be conducted both before and after the summer months.

4.1.4 Phase 4: Consolidation and Reflection

Phase 3 will produce ideas for interventions and strategies that can be used by different stakeholders to overcome the barriers identified in phase 2. In between phases 2 and 3, the researcher team will consolidate these results, and refine them to produce a set of concrete, coherent interventions. These interventions will also be discussed with the CG prior to the start of phase 4. The objective of phase 4 is, then, to collectively reflect upon and refine the interventions.

Two special topics, summarized in table 6 below, will guide the direction of refinement and reflection on the intervention strategies. Stakeholders will be gathered in heterogeneous groups, and two sessions per special topic will be conducted. All of the sessions within this phase will begin with a researcher-led presentation on the results of the SH engagement plan so far, specifically highlighting the different interventions and strategies that were co-created in phase 3.

The first of the special topics is “new use cases and business models”. In these sessions, the objectives will be to co-create ideas for new blockchain-based use-cases and business models that can make use of, accelerate, or adapt to the broader changes that may be instigated by the different interventions. The second topic concerns social and environmental responsibility. In these sessions, the objective will be to, first, discuss the potential social and environmental impact of the interventions and, second, to adapt the intervention strategies to improve the potential (positive) social and environmental impact of each strategy. This phase aims to *refine* and *adapt* the interventions subject to these criteria, and it does not explicitly aim to co-create new interventions.

This final phase of the WGs will take place in November and December 2024 (Figure 4).

Table 6. *Special topic areas for discussion in phase 4*

New use cases and business models
Social and environmental responsibility

4.2 Local Focus Groups (FGs)

In parallel to the working groups at the European level, local focus groups at the national level will be conducted. The purpose of local focus group discussions on blockchain applications in the agri-food supply chain is to gather insights, opinions, and feedback from stakeholders who are directly involved in or affected by the agri-food industry at a local level. These discussions aim to explore the potential benefits, challenges, and opportunities that BCT can bring to the agri-food supply chain, paying particular attention to local, contextual conditions that would enhance or limit the development and uptake of BCT in agri-food chains. The specific purposes of conducting local focus group discussions are as follows:

- 1. Understanding Stakeholder Needs:** Focus group discussions provide a platform to engage with various stakeholders such as farmers, suppliers, distributors, retailers, consumers, and regulatory authorities. By actively involving these stakeholders, the discussions can help identify their needs, concerns, and expectations related to the agri-food supply chain.
- 2. Identifying Use Cases:** Through local focus group discussions, participants can brainstorm and explore potential use cases of blockchain technology in the agri-food industry. They can collectively identify areas where blockchain can bring value, such as traceability, product authenticity, supply chain transparency, and quality control.
- 3. Assessing Feasibility:** Local focus groups allow stakeholders to assess the feasibility of implementing blockchain solutions in the local agri-food supply chain. Participants can discuss the infrastructure requirements, technical capabilities, cost considerations, and regulatory implications associated with implementing BCT in the specific country-context (e.g., also in relation to cultural and legislative limits).
- 4. Addressing Challenges:** Focus group discussions help in identifying and addressing the challenges and barriers that may arise during the implementation of blockchain applications in the agri-food supply chain. Participants can share their concerns and suggest strategies to overcome hurdles such as interoperability, data privacy, scalability, and adoption.
- 5. Generating Insights:** These discussions enable the generation of valuable insights and perspectives from diverse stakeholders. By bringing together individuals with different roles and expertise, focus groups can foster innovative ideas and unique viewpoints that may lead to new approaches and solutions for improving the agri-food supply chain.
- 6. Facilitating Collaboration:** Local focus groups provide a collaborative environment where stakeholders can share knowledge, experiences, and best practices. They promote networking, partnership building, and collaboration among participants, encouraging collective efforts to drive positive change in the agri-food industry.

Overall, the purpose of local focus group discussions on blockchain applications in the agri-food supply chain is to create an inclusive and participatory process that empowers local stakeholders to shape the development and implementation of blockchain solutions, ensuring they are aligned with the specific needs and realities of their local communities.

The local focus groups will be executed by project partners as this will allow for conducting in local languages. In each country two focus groups (lasting about, 2-3 hours) will be conducted at minimum, to allow for sufficiently diverse data gathering. To allow for cross-country comparison, it is of benefit to organize all local focus groups according to the same protocol. To

accommodate local conditions for travel, all focus groups will therefore be conducted online, unless there are clear reasons to deviate from this, in which case an exemption will be discussed with the Work package leader and the project coordinator. The first focus group should include stakeholders from groups SH1-SH4; the second from SH5-SH8. Per focus group, at minimum 6 and at maximum 12 stakeholders should attend. The project partners will be trained prior to that, to ensure we have got a common understanding, approach, and methods across the national focus groups. To facilitate comparison, the local focus groups will be recorded, audio transcribed and translated into English.

Audio transcription and transcript cleaning should take place within 2 weeks after the focus groups was conducted. Translation into the English language should follow the week after. This will ensure the transcript closely resembles interactions that took place during the meeting and allow the consortium to learn from findings in different local focus groups. Project participants are also encouraged to share field notes on the data collection, to further enhance data analysis. Analysis of the transcripts will be conducted by Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Athena Institute, based on thematic analysis. Findings will be checked with project partners to ensure valid interpretation of transcripts. As qualitative data collection is always subject to the willingness and ability of stakeholders to engage, exemptions to the approach discussed above are possible, after careful consideration of options, alternative approaches and contingencies with the Work package leader and project coordinator.

Special topic areas:

Influence of local contextual factors on perspectives
Experiences and opportunities for making use of blockchain technology
Strategies to present blockchain technology effectively

4.3. (Strategic) Clustering Group (CG)

The main target are policymakers and advocacy players, selected both at the EU and national levels (third countries representatives should not be excluded – role of WFO/NSCE to be taken into consideration).

The aim of this group is to bring to them the feedback and results got from the WG meetings and obtain advice/recommendations/policy updates for continuing our remaining activities. It is expected to have approx. 3-4 meetings of 1,5/2 hours each along the project lifespan, led by TCA. Other partners' involvement to be better defined.

In this project, the cluster will consists of experts in blockchain technology and specialists from institutions and other policy initiatives/programmes at EU/national level. The group will be chaired by CERTH; support from EC project officer will be required to endorse the initiative from policy point of view. Such group will meet periodically (physically or virtually) and will act at EU level. The group will share insights and evidence, sharing in this way the knowledge generated outside and inside the consortium and the future strategies. The preliminary list of organisations to be represented in the cluster include representatives renowned for playing an important role in advocacy and representation of the agri-food supply chain.

In particular, the clustering group in the context of stakeholder engagement serves as a mechanism to organize and facilitate effective communication, collaboration, and participation between consortium and stakeholders in charge of policy decisions. The purpose of the clustering group in stakeholder engagement is as follows:

1. **Enhanced communication:** By grouping stakeholders based on their commonalities, such as policy makers and other experts, clustering group provides a structured platform for targeted communication.
2. **Tailored engagement strategies:** Clustering group allows for the customization of engagement strategies to cater to the specific needs, preferences, and characteristics of different stakeholder clusters. Each cluster may have distinct priorities, knowledge levels, and communication preferences. By understanding these differences, engagement efforts can be tailored to ensure that stakeholders receive relevant information, have their voices heard, and participate meaningfully in the decision-making processes. This tailored approach increases the effectiveness and inclusiveness of stakeholder engagement.
3. **Collaboration and consensus-building:** As the stakeholder engagement activities are meant to develop a roadmap on the application of blockchain in the agri-food supply chain, clustering group promotes collaboration and consensus-building among stakeholders who share common interests or objectives. By bringing together stakeholders with aligned goals, clustering groups provide a platform for collective problem-solving, sharing of best practices, and joint decision-making. This collaborative approach helps to build trust, identify shared priorities, and generate innovative solutions that reflect the collective interests of the clustered stakeholders.
4. **Representation and advocacy:** Clustering group can serve as representative body or advocacy platform. By consolidating the voices and concerns of stakeholders within a cluster, these groups can amplify their collective influence and advocate for their interests. This strengthens the representation of stakeholders in engagement processes, ensures their perspectives are adequately considered, and increases the likelihood of achieving outcomes that align with their needs.

4.4 Inter-sectoral Task Forces (TFs)

The Task Force is a homogeneous group of experts on blockchain with no boundary in the sector applied. The aim for the task forces is to elaborate on blockchain subjects and translate the ideas into high level strategic documents. The inter-sectoral Task Force members will be identified from ongoing ICT/blockchain related projects, and it will bring together the different experts from different domain to jointly discuss on topics such as:

- a) Interoperability
- b) Standardization
- c) Regulation
- d) Skills

Touching such topics, 2-3 task forces will be established. To avoid conflicts/overlaps, when one TF will end the other one will start. There is no obligation for the experts to stick in just one TF, but they can be part of more than one if experience and expertise are aligned.

Starting from the assumption that the agri-food sector can learn from other (more advanced) sectors, the purpose of inter-sectoral task forces is to promote cross-sector collaboration, coordination, and collective action towards shared goals.

Each task force will bring together around thirty stakeholders, but not all of them should necessarily attend each single meeting.

According to the nature of the group, not all the project partners will be involved: only the technical ones [CERTH ITI+IBO, ENG, COMP, FHG/Koblenz, INOV/INESC ID] + Project Coordinator. All these above-mentioned partners will contribute both to the experts' identification (according to their knowledge and Network of contacts from other projects), recruitment and will attend the TFs meetings for providing inputs.

As the meetings put a strong emphasis on exchange and networking, icebreakers and energizers will be used while participatory methods will be included in the agenda and Athena will contribute.

Here are some key purposes of inter-sectoral task forces in stakeholder engagement:

1. **Holistic problem solving:** Inter-sectoral task forces allow stakeholders from diverse sectors to come together and collectively address complex, multifaceted problems or opportunities. By leveraging the expertise, resources, and perspectives of stakeholders from different sectors, these task forces facilitate a comparison between sectorial experiences and a more comprehensive and holistic approach to problem-solving. This collaborative effort increases the chances of finding innovative and sustainable solutions that take into account various dimensions and interdependencies of the issue at hand.
2. **Knowledge sharing and learning:** Inter-sectoral task forces provide a platform for knowledge sharing, learning, and exchange of best practices among stakeholders from different sectors. Each sector brings unique insights, experiences, and expertise that can benefit others in understanding the challenges, opportunities, and potential strategies. This collaborative learning environment promotes cross-sectoral understanding, fosters innovation, and helps stakeholders expand their knowledge and skills beyond their own sector.
3. **Policy and strategy development:** Inter-sectoral task forces play a crucial role in informing policy and strategy development processes. By bringing together stakeholders from different sectors, these task forces provide valuable input, insights, and recommendations that can influence policy decisions, regulatory frameworks, and strategic planning. The collaborative nature of these task forces enhances the legitimacy and relevance of the resulting policies and strategies.
4. **Advocacy and influence:** Inter-sectoral task forces can serve as advocacy platforms to collectively influence policies, practices, or public opinion. By presenting a unified voice and representing multiple sectors, the task forces can advocate for change, promote shared values, and drive collective action towards desired outcomes. This advocacy strengthens the influence and impact of stakeholder engagement efforts.

Differently from the other groups, TFs will not be only discussion meetings; inside the group there will be identified some external people who will take the leadership of developing some concepts and drafting paragraphs/chapters of the White Paper(s). The White Paper will be thus a multi-handed document. CERTH will lead the group and edit the overall document(s).

At least three meetings per Topic will be foreseen, mostly carried out in remote mode. One TF group meeting could take place in person during Synergy Days (organised each year by SmartAgriHubs³), or the Project meeting in Thessaloniki, in April-June 2024

Benefits for TF participant: co-authorship of the generated strategic Position/White Paper.

A big final event to launch the White Papers should be organized in Brussels, hybrid. Suggestion to take place during other events: European Week of Regions and Cities (Oct) / Horizon Europe Info Days.

Criteria for selection of experts:

- Career (senior)
- Commitment
- Gender balance
- Geographicity
- Involvement in ongoing similar projects
- knowledge of the English language

³ <https://www.smartagrihubs.eu/synergy-days>

5. Implementation

5.1 Stakeholder involvement mode

5.1.1. Steps for involvement

In order to participate, each stakeholder is asked to fill in an 'Expression of Interest'. Stakeholder Board members will be included in an internal list (mapping). Invitation to single sessions/meetings will be at the discretion of the project partners, depending on the topic under discussion, number of people expected to sit around the table, type of target and related expertise. Invitation will be done two weeks in advance and will be done in written form (e-mail) – if needed, a phone call can follow. The invitation will define the type of meeting (virtual or in person), if a pre-meeting is scheduled, will contain the Agenda of the meeting (specifying the topic under discussion), the duration, the other type of stakeholders invited, the role expected by the individual, the expected output, a request for Informed Consent. It is up to the member to accept or not the invitation. In case the invitation is declined, the project team will identify another individual. The process will continue until the minimum number of expected participants is reached.

In case a stakeholder cannot attend for unexpected reasons, it is required the communication in advance to find a substitute and/or manage the absence.

5.1.2. Parameters for invitation

For each session/meeting, the consortium wants to create a maximally effective researcher-stakeholder team. Following a **purposive** method, identification and invitation of specific individuals will be based on criteria determined by researchers, starting from the topic under discussion as well as the questions which will guide the discussion (e.g. their expertise or experience, capacity, motivation, training requirements and equity and diversity in the team).

Steps before each meeting:

1. Preparation of the Topic and questions which will guide the discussion (inside the consortium)
2. Consideration of the broad stakeholder type(s) we want to engage (homogeneous or heterogeneous groups)
3. Identification of the individuals to involve who may be of relevance to the Group
4. Clarification of the role each individual brings into the meeting (e.g. there is often overlap between stakeholder types and roles may not be tidy and structured, for example a researcher may also be a farmer. If we are aiming to find a stakeholder to represent a certain stakeholder type, it is important to remember that whilst this can be mutually agreed with the stakeholder, each individual brings a unique set of experiences and cannot be expected to represent all views within a stakeholder group)

For facilitating the individuals' selection, it may be useful to consider the following questions:

- What decisions will the meeting make?
- How are selected stakeholders affected by this topic?
- What is the number of people we would like to and can realistically engage at the scope?

5.2 Collaborative meeting tools: digital tools for interaction and co-creation

On a case-by-case basis, the following (not exhaustive list of) tools will be taken into consideration for animating the discussion:

Miro: online collaborative whiteboard platform that enables distributed teams to work effectively together, from brainstorming with digital sticky notes to planning and managing agile workflows.

Mentimeter: is a presentation tool that is designed to work digitally, live. It's built both for use in presence as well as for remote connection. This tool allows moderators to interact with the stakeholders in real time, take a poll, present a quiz, and more.

Mural: is a virtual space where you can visually and interactively collaborate with team members (both hybrid and remote). Once created the dashboards, participants can work and collaborate on any type of project together with other members. Brainstorming and idea generation, meetings and workshops, strategy and planning, design and analysis – Mural can be for any task. It is simple to use, intuitive, and extremely effective.

Google Jamboards: Jamboard is a digital whiteboard that lets you collaborate in real time using either the Jamboard device, web browser or mobile app.

Where new collaborative tools should emerge on the market, will be included into the list as well.

5.3 Collaborative consultation methods

Both traditional and innovative consultation methods will be used. In addition to the primary methods described above (e.g., backcasting and various methods for co-creation and co-design) and others, the following are examples of complementary methods that may be employed throughout the stakeholder engagement sessions:

- **World Café:** Informal meetings between people (conversations in bars, salons, at the barbershop, etc.) have historically been opportunities for exchange, participation and learning, as well as preparation for social action. The objective of a World Café is to make available the power of informal conversations in order to creatively mobilize thoughts and resources, produce learning, share knowledge, and ultimately generate change. In practice, the intimate and welcoming atmosphere of a café is recreated, with round tables suitable for seating 4 to 6 people each. The tables are arranged freely in a room and are equipped with materials for annotating, drawing, writing, in other words, for fixing ideas. It is a simple and effective method of starting informal, lively, and constructive conversations on issues and topics of common interest. According to the theory underlying this tool, the evolution of ideas in a World Café takes place through an invitation to all participants to move from one discussion group to another in a rather short time.
- **Best Practice Forums (BPFs):** The objective is to collect existing and emerging good practices from community experience, not to develop new policies or practices. BPFs are open, bottom-up, and collective processes to produce community-driven outputs.

5.4 Consultation plan

The project team created an internal consultation plan in detail which depicts timing, topics, and interconnections between groups. It will guide the project team actions. However, it is not a static document and will be constantly reconfirmed or partially revised, in full compliance with the strategies and objectives that the consortium has set.

5.5 Risk management – Mitigation and Contingency

During the implementation phase of stakeholder engagement several risks and challenges may arise. It is important to be aware of these risks and respond appropriately to mitigate them. Here are the expected risks related to the implementation phase and strategies for mitigation and contingency:

1. **Low number of adhesions:** Along the recruitment phase, some stakeholders identified as experienced may show low interest for the stakeholder board.

Mitigation: Conduct early and ongoing stakeholder analysis to identify potential areas of conflict or resistance. Be sure to offer a targeted message according to the individual in front of us. Provide opportunities for stakeholders to ask questions, seek clarification, and provide feedback. Create new opportunities to increase the number of people to be contacted

2. **Lack of Stakeholder Participation:** There is a risk that some stakeholders may not actively participate or engage in the activities, which can hinder the effectiveness of the engagement process.

Mitigation: Conduct a thorough stakeholder analysis to identify key stakeholders and their motivations. Develop targeted communication strategies to inform stakeholders about the benefits and importance of their participation. Provide opportunities for stakeholders to clarify their concerns and provide resolution.

3. **Miscommunication or Misunderstanding:** Communication breakdowns or misunderstandings on Stakeholder Board scope and their specific role can lead to confusion, conflicts, or misinformation.

Mitigation: Establish clear communication channels and guidelines. Use various communication methods, such as meetings, workshops, online platforms, and written materials to ensure information is disseminated effectively. Provide opportunities for stakeholders to ask questions, seek clarification, and provide feedback. Regularly review and update communication materials to address any emerging concerns or misconceptions. Proactively address concerns and provide information to alleviate doubts or misconceptions. Foster an environment of open dialogue and active listening to understand stakeholder perspectives and address their concerns. Seek to find common ground and explore win-win solutions that benefit all parties involved.

4. **Data Privacy and Security:** Collecting and managing stakeholder data may pose privacy and security risks.

Mitigation: Comply with relevant data protection regulations and ensure stakeholder consent is obtained for data collection and usage. Implement robust data security measures, such as encryption, access controls, and regular data backups. Clearly communicate how stakeholder data will be used, stored, and protected. Train staff on data privacy and security best practices.

5. **Gradual withdrawal:** Being on a voluntary basis and free, individuals can decide to give up at any time

Mitigation: Understanding of the reasons, to avoid that there are patterns, recurring issues, or systemic problems and thus areas that require improvement within the consultation process. In case the reasons are independent from the project (e.g. personal issues, professional limits), the list will be checked for confirming that other substitutes with similar skills are available, otherwise restart the engagement process.

6. **External Factors and Events:** External factors such as economic changes, regulatory shifts, or natural disasters can impact stakeholder engagement activities.

Contingency: Continuously monitor external factors and adapt engagement strategies accordingly. Have contingency plans in place to address unforeseen events or changes

in the operating environment. Maintain open lines of communication with stakeholders to keep them informed of any changes or disruptions and adjust engagement activities as needed. Regularly reviewing and assessing risks, as well as adapting mitigation and contingency plans as necessary, will help ensure the success and effectiveness of stakeholder engagement activities.

- 7. Challenges in maintaining stakeholders relationships:** Once the stakeholder is included into the list, it may take some time for them to become involved and even if the groups will be active it is excluded that all will attend to each meeting.

Contingency: It is important to maintain active relationships with each stakeholder. The periodic Newsletter and some periodic alerts will make up for this purpose.

- 8. Concerns and complaints:** Stakeholder complaints cannot be excluded. How these complaints are handled can significantly impact the project's reputation, stakeholder satisfaction, and overall success. An internal process for complaint management will be set up for quick and fair resolutions.

Contingency: Stakeholder complaints provide valuable feedback and insights into areas that require improvement within the organisation, for this reason the information gathered from complaints will be used to identify patterns, recurring issues, or systemic problems.

By proactively identifying and addressing these risks, and implementing appropriate mitigation strategies, the implementation phase of blockchain applications in the agri-food supply value chain can be more successful and effective. Regular monitoring, feedback loops, and continuous improvement efforts are essential to mitigate these risks and ensure the success of the stakeholder engagement.

5.6 Resources for implementation

For the success of the SEP, sufficient resources are needed to undertake the engagement, both in terms of project team effort, investments and promotion of stakeholder involvement.

With regard to human resources, project partners in the consortium will provide the necessary expertise and knowledge on blockchain technology, agri-food supply chain processes, and related regulations. Project partners will play a big role in stakeholder identification and recruitment, in maintaining them involved, as well as in the preparation and carrying out of meetings (as organizers/moderators, in a case-by-case basis).

Stakeholder engagement sessions will be facilitated by the Athena Institute- Vrije University Amsterdam, with support from other partners (for example, to discuss highly technical topics that are the expertise of other consortium members). In such situations, members of the Athena Institute team will provide training as necessary to other consortium members.

The project will benefit from the contribution by project partners but if needed, external consultants or advisors with relevant experience to provide guidance and support will be considered.

The vast majority of the sessions described above will be conducted online. This will allow stakeholders across Europe to contribute, while the costs for joining sessions will be limited. Conducting such research in an online medium poses its own methodological challenges but has the benefit of significantly reducing the amount of resources that would normally be required to gather participants in person. Current cyber communication methods necessitated by Covid-

19 effectively demonstrated to be valid as well, maintaining teams united, presenting productivity increases, reduced costs, and other practical benefits. Since the Covid-19 pandemic, the number of researchers engaging with online, qualitative methods such as those we propose above, has increased significantly (e.g., Poliandri et al, 2023). Methodological insights from other researchers engaging in these methods will be taken into account throughout the planning of each individual session. Conducting focus groups and co-creation sessions online presents challenges, as certain aspects of in-person interaction cannot be perfectly translated (Keen et al, 2022). However, the online format also offers an opportunity to explore innovative approaches to engaging participants online, such as experimentation with different visualization tools (ibid).

Some of the best practices for online methods, as laid out by Poliandri et al, include careful selection of the online medium, and providing support to participants with relatively little technological expertise (2023). The exact online medium will be flexible based on the preferences of participants, with Microsoft Teams acting as the default platform due to internal norms and the automatic transcription feature, which can aid in streamlining analysis. Other options include GoToMeeting and Zoom, among others. Where necessary, technical support and guidance (e.g. rehearsals/pre-meetings) will be provided to participants so that they are able to engage in the discussion sessions seamlessly.

The local focus groups, in general, represent the exceptions from the above resource requirements. Local FGs, in contrast to the other sessions outlined in this plan, have the option of being conducted in person and in the participants' native language (i.e., not English). Further, focus groups will be, as mentioned above, primarily led by consortium partners based in the country in question. Therefore, additional resources may be required to support the local focus groups.

In order to conduct the local focus group sessions effectively, consortium members may require training on transdisciplinary facilitation techniques, which will be provided by the Athena Institute. In the event that local focus groups are conducted in person, additional resources will be required to procure a venue for the sessions [to be dealt with by the local consortium partners]. Additionally, translation services may be required for sessions not conducted in English, although it is possible that local consortium partners can provide these services. The main costs will be for transcribing from local languages to English to facilitate data analysis.

As said, promotion of the Stakeholder Board requires some investment: e.g. maintenance of the website, campaign on Social Media (also on payment, if the adhesion should be low), participation to Conferences/Fairs (with booth) where stakeholders participate.

5.7 Reporting stakeholder engagement

Reporting allows to i) share the knowledge generated along the project through the stakeholder engagement, ii) critically assess impact and success, iii) enhance the evidence base of stakeholder engagement in research and provides resources, examples, and encouragement to other researchers in joining the project, and iv) ensure fair acknowledgement of stakeholder time and effort.

At month 24 and M30 it is scheduled to report activities carried out under the form of Deliverables (PU – Public, fully open - will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page after approval) and later on the project's website.

Also, after ensuring permission is sought, stakeholders can be acknowledged via co-authorship of publications, documentation in methods of reports, or mentioning within acknowledgements sections of publications (Haddaway et al., 2017).

5.8 Monitoring and Evaluation

Monitoring of the stakeholder engagement process allows the efficacy of the process to be evaluated. Specifically, by identifying key performance indicators (KPIs) that reflect the objectives of the SEP and the specific actions and timings, it is possible to both monitor and evaluate the process undertaken.

Two distinct but related monitoring activities will be implemented:

- During the engagement activities: short-term monitoring to allow for adjustments/improvements to be made (e.g. geographical balance, gender balance, skills balance, etc.)
- Following completion of all engagement activities: review of outputs to evaluate the effectiveness of the SEP as implemented.

5.9 Special considerations for gender and inclusivity: core values

When engaging with stakeholders, the project will consider gender and inclusivity to ensure that diverse perspectives are heard and valued. Here are some special considerations to promote gender and inclusivity in stakeholder engagement:

- 1. Diverse representation:** The stakeholder engagement will strive for diverse representation among the participants. Individuals from different genders, socioeconomic backgrounds, and other underrepresented groups will be provided an opportunity to participate. The motivation is to actively seek diverse voices and perspectives.
- 2. Equal participation:** Emphasis will be put on creating an inclusive environment where all stakeholders feel comfortable and encouraged to participate. Effort will be put towards avoiding any biases or discrimination that may hinder certain individuals from fully engaging. The ultimate goal is to provide equal opportunities for all stakeholders to contribute and be heard. It will be beneficial to ensure that stakeholders are representative of the diversity found in the agri-food sector, including small-scale farmers and other marginalized actors.
- 3. Sensitivity to cultural norms:** The project will recognize and respect cultural norms and practices that may affect stakeholder participation such as potential gender-based barriers and adapt the approach accordingly. The engagement methods will be designed to ensure that they are culturally sensitive and inclusive.
- 4. Language and communication:** The project will use clear and inclusive language in the communication materials and during engagement sessions. Since blockchain is associated with many technical terms, measures will be put in place to avoid jargon or

6. Data management techniques

When managing data in the project, it is essential to adhere to specific principles to ensure data integrity, security, and transparency. Here are the key data management principles that will guide the project:

- 1. Data Privacy:** The stakeholder engagement activities will protect the privacy of individuals' data by implementing appropriate privacy controls and adhering to relevant data protection regulations. Much emphasis will be on minimising the collection and storage of personally identifiable information to what is necessary for the project's objectives. Data will be shared only with EC, nominated reviewers and not with third parties.
- 2. Data Security:** The project will implement robust security measures to protect data from unauthorized access, alteration, or loss. This will involve the use of encryption techniques, access controls, and secure data storage to ensure the confidentiality and integrity of the data. Best practices will be implemented for secure coding and the security protocols will be regularly updated.
- 3. Data Governance:** Clear data governance policies and procedures will be established to define roles, responsibilities, and processes related to data management. Guidelines will be developed to define data ownership, data quality standards, and mechanisms for data validation and verification. Measures will be taken to ensure compliance with EU standards and regulations.
- 4. Data Consistency and Accuracy:** To maintain consistent and accurate data across the agri-food supply chain, the project will implement data validation mechanisms, conduct regular checks, and ensure proper data verification.
- 5. Data Interoperability:** To facilitate data interoperability among different stakeholders in the supply chain, the project will use standardized data formats, protocols, and focus group discussion guides to ensure seamless data exchange and integration between various systems and platforms. Measures will be put in place to ensure compatibility and consistency in data representation across various stages of the stakeholder engagement activities.
- 6. Data Lifecycle Management:** A comprehensive data lifecycle management strategy will be developed in which data retention policies, archival procedures, and secure data disposal mechanisms in compliance with legal and regulatory requirements will be defined. Proper backup and disaster recovery procedures to protect against data loss will be put in place.
- 7. Stakeholder Engagement and Consent:** Consent for data collection, sharing, and usage will be sought from all stakeholders who will participate in the engagement activities. It will be required contextually to the invitation to a specific session/meeting. Transparency with stakeholders about how their data is being used will be emphasized to ensure their understanding and agreement with the project's data management practices.
- 8. Continuous Improvement:** The project will regularly review and enhance data management practices based on feedback, evolving technologies, and changing regulatory landscapes. This will be done to stay up to date with best practices, standards, and emerging trends in data management.

By following these data management principles, the project is expected to establish a robust and trustworthy data management framework on the application of blockchain technology in the agri-food supply chain project.

7. Conclusion

This plan elaborates the stakeholder engagement plan which has been designed to provide input to shed light on the current partial and fragmented picture of blockchain technology applications in the agri-food domain, by clarifying both the benefits and risks which the technology entails. It draws from diverse stakeholder engagement methods, which provides opportunities to explore and apply the best fitting methods. While managing contingencies for risks, the aim is to draw-up a Roadmap for blockchain technologies in the agri-food sector, based on consolidated and balanced stakeholder consultation process. However, stakeholder engagement is always unpredictable and is it important to detect signals at an early stage so as to take mitigatory measures. Even if the plan has been drafted with a reasonable level of accuracy, since the project is still at an early stage and some external factors can change the perspectives (e.g., regulations, market, etc), the document will be revised along the project lifespan to confirm or eventually realign contents.

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